

Assessment and Alterations in Retinal Nerve Fiber Layer Thickness before and Following Glaucoma Filtration Surgery Using Optical Coherence Tomography: A Clinical Study

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Abstract:

Background: Glaucoma is a major cause of irreversible blindness worldwide, primarily characterized by elevated intraocular pressure (IOP) leading to progressive damage to the optic nerve. Glaucoma filtration surgery is a common intervention aimed at reducing IOP and preventing further optic nerve damage. Advances in optical coherence tomography (OCT) have enabled precise measurement of retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) thickness, which is a critical indicator of optic nerve health. This study aimed to evaluate changes in RNFL thickness before and after glaucoma filtration surgery using OCT and to explore the correlation between these changes and visual outcomes.

Methods: In a prospective observational study conducted, 100 participants undergoing glaucoma filtration surgery were assessed. Preoperative and postoperative OCT measurements of RNFL thickness were recorded. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with paired t-tests used to compare preoperative and postoperative RNFL measurements.

Results: The mean preoperative RNFL thickness was 85.3 micrometers (SD = 10.1), which increased to 88.5 micrometers (SD = 9.4) six months post-surgery. This increase was statistically significant ($t = -7.45$, $p < 0.001$). A moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.01$) was observed between changes in RNFL thickness and improvements in visual acuity. Minor postoperative complications included transient ocular discomfort in 10% of participants and mild IOP spikes in 5% of cases.

Conclusion: Glaucoma filtration surgery significantly improved RNFL thickness, suggesting beneficial effects on optic nerve health. The positive correlation between increased RNFL thickness and improved visual acuity highlights the potential of this surgery to enhance visual outcomes.

Recommendations: It is recommended that OCT be utilized as a routine follow-up tool in patients undergoing glaucoma filtration surgery to monitor RNFL changes and assess surgical efficacy. Additionally, further research should explore long-term outcomes and the impact of RNFL changes on functional vision.

Keywords: Glaucoma, Retinal Nerve Fiber Layer, Optical Coherence Tomography, Glaucoma Filtration Surgery, Visual Acuity

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Introduction

Glaucoma is a leading cause of irreversible blindness worldwide, characterized by progressive damage to the optic nerve and subsequent loss of vision. The condition is primarily associated with elevated intraocular pressure (IOP), which contributes to the degeneration of retinal nerve fibers [1]. The management of glaucoma aims to reduce IOP and prevent further damage to the optic nerve. One effective surgical intervention for

controlling IOP is glaucoma filtration surgery, which involves creating a new drainage pathway for aqueous humor to alleviate intraocular pressure.

Recent advancements in imaging technology, particularly Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT), have revolutionized the assessment of retinal structures, including the retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL). OCT provides high-resolution, cross-sectional images of the retina, allowing for

precise measurement of RNFL thickness, which is a key indicator of optic nerve health and glaucoma progression [2]. Changes in RNFL thickness can reflect the efficacy of therapeutic interventions, including surgical procedures.

Glaucoma filtration surgery, such as trabeculectomy or tube shunt surgery, is designed to reduce IOP by creating a new drainage pathway for aqueous humor. Postoperative assessment of RNFL thickness using OCT can provide valuable insights into the structural changes occurring in the retina following surgery [3]. Recent studies have demonstrated that successful filtration surgery can lead to improvements in RNFL thickness, suggesting that the procedure may help stabilize or even reverse some of the optic nerve damage associated with glaucoma [4].

The relationship between changes in RNFL thickness and clinical outcomes following glaucoma filtration surgery remains an area of active research. Understanding how RNFL thickness correlates with visual acuity and other functional outcomes can guide clinicians in evaluating the success of the surgery and in tailoring postoperative management strategies.

This study aims to evaluate changes in retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) thickness before and after glaucoma filtration surgery using optical coherence tomography (OCT). The study utilized a prospective observational approach to assess the impact of the surgical intervention on RNFL thickness.

Methodology

Study Design: A clinical study.

Study Setting: The study took place at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India, spanning from January 2023 to May 2023 (6 months).

Participants: The study included 100 participants who were scheduled for glaucoma filtration surgery. Participants were recruited from the ophthalmology department of the hospital.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with primary open-angle glaucoma requiring filtration surgery.
- Age between 18 and 80 years.
- Informed consent obtained from the participants.
- Ability to comply with follow-up visits and procedures.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with secondary glaucoma or other ocular pathologies that could affect RNFL thickness.

- History of previous ocular surgery other than cataract extraction.
- Patients with systemic conditions affecting retinal health, such as diabetes mellitus or hypertension, uncontrolled at the time of study entry.
- Inability to provide informed consent.

Bias: To minimize bias, the study employed random selection of participants from the pool of eligible candidates. Blinding of the OCT measurement technicians to the clinical details of the participants. Standardized OCT procedures to ensure consistency in measurements. Regular monitoring and audit of the study procedures and data collection process

Data Collection

Data were collected at two time points:

1. Preoperative Assessment: OCT measurements of RNFL thickness were recorded prior to the glaucoma filtration surgery.
2. Postoperative Assessment: Follow-up OCT measurements were performed 6 months after the surgery to assess changes in RNFL thickness.

Procedure

1. Preoperative Examination:
 - Participants underwent a comprehensive ophthalmic examination, including visual acuity testing, intraocular pressure measurement, and fundoscopic evaluation.
 - Baseline OCT measurements of RNFL thickness were obtained before the surgical procedure.
2. Surgical Intervention:
 - Glaucoma filtration surgery was performed according to standard surgical protocols.
 - Postoperative care was provided, and participants were monitored for any immediate surgical complications.
3. Postoperative Follow-Up:
 - Participants were scheduled for follow-up visits at 6 months post-surgery.
 - Repeat OCT measurements were conducted to evaluate changes in RNFL thickness.

Statistical Analysis: Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic and baseline characteristics of the participants. Paired t-test or Wilcoxon signed-rank test (depending on data distribution) compared RNFL thickness before and after surgery. Correlation analysis assessed the relationship between changes in RNFL thickness

and clinical outcomes. p -values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Result

A total of 100 participants (60 males, 40 females) were included in the study. The mean age of participants was 65.2 years (SD = 8.4). Baseline characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Total Participants	100
Male	60 (60%)
Female	40 (40%)
Age (Years)	Mean = 65.2 (SD = 8.4)
Preoperative IOP (mmHg)	Mean = 21.8 (SD = 3.2)
Visual Acuity (LogMAR)	Mean = 0.6 (SD = 0.3)

The mean preoperative RNFL thickness was 85.3 micrometers (SD = 10.1). The distribution of RNFL thickness measurements is detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Preoperative RNFL Thickness

RNFL Thickness (μm)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
70 - 79	15	15
80 - 89	40	40
90 - 99	30	30
100 - 109	10	10
110 - 119	5	5

Six months post-surgery, the mean RNFL thickness was 88.5 micrometers (SD = 9.4). The changes in RNFL thickness are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Postoperative RNFL Thickness

RNFL Thickness (μm)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
70 - 79	10	10
80 - 89	25	25
90 - 99	40	40
100 - 109	20	20
110 - 119	5	5

The mean change in RNFL thickness was 3.2 micrometers (SD = 1.8). This increase was statistically significant, as detailed in Table 4.

Table 4: Change in RNFL Thickness

RNFL Thickness Change (μm)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
< 0	5	5
0 - 2	20	20
2 - 4	45	45
4 - 6	25	25
> 6	5	5

The paired t -test revealed a statistically significant increase in RNFL thickness postoperatively ($t = -7.45$, $p < 0.001$). The mean RNFL thickness increased from 85.3 micrometers preoperatively to 88.5 micrometers postoperatively.

Table 5: Statistical Analysis of RNFL Thickness

Measurement	Mean (μm)	SD (μm)	t-value	p-value
Preoperative	85.3	10.1		
Postoperative	88.5	9.4	-7.45	< 0.001

The correlation between the change in RNFL thickness and improvement in visual acuity was analyzed. A moderate positive correlation was found ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that greater increases in RNFL thickness were associated with better visual outcomes.

Table 6: Correlation between RNFL Thickness Change and Visual Acuity Improvement

Correlation Coefficient	p-value
0.45	< 0.01

No serious complications were reported. Minor postoperative issues included transient ocular discomfort in 10% of participants and mild intraocular pressure spikes in 5% of cases, which were managed with topical medications.

Discussion

The study aimed to evaluate changes in retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) thickness before and after glaucoma filtration surgery using optical coherence tomography (OCT). The analysis included 100 participants, with a mean age of 65.2 years, and a baseline RNFL thickness of 85.3 micrometers.

Preoperative measurements revealed that RNFL thickness ranged predominantly between 80 and 99 micrometers. Post-surgery, there was a notable increase in RNFL thickness, with a mean measurement of 88.5 micrometers. This increase was statistically significant, as evidenced by the paired t-test ($t = -7.45$, $p < 0.001$), indicating a meaningful improvement in RNFL thickness following the surgical intervention.

The data showed that the majority of participants experienced an increase in RNFL thickness ranging from 2 to 4 micrometers, with 45% of participants falling into this category. Only a small percentage experienced a decrease or a change greater than 6 micrometers. The observed increase in RNFL thickness suggests a positive surgical outcome, reflecting potential improvements in the structural integrity of the retina postoperatively.

Additionally, a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.01$) was found between the increase in RNFL thickness and improvements in visual acuity. This suggests that patients who showed greater increases in RNFL thickness also tended to have better visual outcomes, underscoring the potential clinical benefit of the surgery.

Overall, the results indicate that glaucoma filtration surgery effectively improves RNFL thickness, which may be associated with better visual outcomes. The study also reported minor postoperative issues, which were manageable with standard care. These findings support the effectiveness of glaucoma filtration surgery in enhancing retinal nerve fiber health and potentially improving visual function in patients with glaucoma.

A study assessed changes in the neuroretinal rim and retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) in 54 eyes with primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) before and after glaucoma filtration surgery (trabeculectomy or deep sclerectomy).

Postoperative intraocular pressure (IOP) significantly decreased, resulting in a substantial increase in the thickness of the neuroretinal rim and RNFL. No significant changes were observed in the Bruch's membrane opening area. The pressure-related increase in minimum rim width (MRW) correlated with postoperative IOP and cup-to-disc ratio [5].

A multicenter study evaluated 29 eyes undergoing filtration surgery and 25 control eyes. Significant increases in rim area and decreases in cup/disc ratios were observed postoperatively. However, no significant change in mean RNFL thickness was found, though macular parameters improved significantly up to two months after surgery. Correlation between structural changes and IOP reduction was significant for some topographic parameters [6].

A study compared RNFL thickness changes in 40 glaucomatous eyes and 40 non-glaucomatous controls after phacoemulsification. The mean change in RNFL thickness from baseline was significantly greater in glaucomatous eyes than in non-glaucomatous eyes. Both groups experienced a significant decrease in IOP postoperatively [7].

A study analyzed RNFL thickness changes in 40 eyes with POAG before and after trabeculectomy. While IOP significantly decreased postoperatively, no significant changes were found in RNFL thickness or visual field parameters, indicating that RNFL may remain stable despite significant IOP reduction [8].

A longitudinal study observed 71 eyes with normal-tension glaucoma (NTG). Eyes with parapapillary choroidal microvasculature dropout (MvD) had a thinner RNFL and a faster rate of RNFL loss compared to eyes without MvD. The presence of MvD was a significant predictor of RNFL thinning [9].

Conclusion

Glaucoma filtration surgery effectively increased retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) thickness, indicating improved optic nerve health postoperatively. The significant enhancement in RNFL thickness, coupled with the positive correlation to better visual acuity, underscores the efficacy of this surgical intervention in managing glaucoma. Regular OCT monitoring post-surgery is recommended to evaluate ongoing improvements and adjust treatment plans accordingly.

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